

GRAMMATICAL ERRORS MADE BY TRANSLATION STUDENTS WHEN TRANSLATING ARABIC ENVIRONMENTAL TEXT INTO ENGLISH

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Abstract:

The current study aims at analyzing the grammatical errors or mistakes made by translation students at English Department (ED) at Jadara University in Jordan. To achieve the purpose of this study, a validated and reliable scientific Arabic text of environmental text as a test was used. It was given to a sample consists of 20 translation students, and the sample was selected randomly from ED. The students were asked to translate the Arabic environmental text into English. The results reveal the most common grammatical problems found are the problem of "Wrong Word Usage" that has achieved the first rank, followed by the use of the "Subject Verb Agreement", and then the problem of "Sentence Fragment" that has got the third rank. The last rank is for the problems of "Pronouns" and "Verb To Be". In the light of study's results, a number of recommendations and further researches were set up.

Keywords: grammatical problems, translation students, environmental text, Jadara University

1. Introduction

Brislin (1976) defines translation as the transferring of thoughts and ideas between languages, while Newmark (1991) defines it as an attempt to replace messages between two languages. Tengku Sepora & Moindjie (2006) define translation as a form of practice in written and in oral forms. Others such as (Catford, 1965; McGuire, 1980) believe that translation is functionally possible, but to a limited extent depending on how much meaning, the translator wants to convey in the target language. They postulate that translation is the rendering of a source text into a target text, while Nida & Taber (1969) maintain that it is a process of finding their equivalence. On the same vein, Darancik (2016, p. 93) argues that translation is strongly linked with the

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appearance of languages as it is simply the transformation of a meaning in one language to an equivalent meaning in the second language.

Farghal & Shunnaq (1999) categorize equivalence into three types; formal, functional and ideational equivalence. Formal equivalence seeks to capture the form of SL expression. Functional equivalence captures the function of the SL expression independently of the image utilized by translating it into a TL expression that performs the same function in the SL text expression. Ideational equivalence aims at conveying the sense of SL expression independently of the functional and the form.

What is interested here is formal equivalence that is embedded in technical translation. Technical translation focuses on denotative meaning other than connotative sense. On the same research line, Shunnaq (1993) states that technical translation is the focal point of transferring of denotative meaning without connotative meanings or aesthetic values implied in the texts, thus, translation becomes very easy and less difficult. Openness or faithlessness in translation depends on the text under analysis.

2. Technical Translation

Farghal (1994) has met Shunnaq (1993) in saying that scientific and technical translations may require less individual intervention from the translator. This is because the issue of equivalence of in such texts simply involves focusing on the denotative meanings. Terms in these texts are typically universal and have been assimilated in all languages. Scientific terms can explicitly illustrate this point. Such terms entail fewer difficulties than other types because of their cultural invariance. In other words, where translation in these fields is seen as simply a question of label swapping, translation scholars seem to naturally have little difficulty in achieving complete lexical equivalence.

On the same research line, Stoian (2016, p. 134) says that technical translation has gained more importance in the field of translation due to the increasing use of various scientific, legal and commercial terms in business, trade and human rights. Despite the negligence of technical translation in theories of translation, nowadays, no one can ignore that it is of a great significance due to the increasing use of new terms in science and technology, and the ever increasing commercial and military transactions between persons and nations.

In summary, AlShehab (2009) says that after considering the different text types, one can say that translation of technical and scientific terms does not involve many problematic areas. The notions involved are universal, frequently having only one standard term to express them in both the source and the target languages and carrying no connotative meanings. These terms are universal and typically address reason rather than emotion. AlShehab (2018) signifies that Environmental Translation (ET) is considered a type of technical translation as it has its own universal terms in both the SL and TL.

Thus, theories of translation are theories of equivalence. Aziz & Lataiwish (2000) say that theories of translation may have two threads; literal theories of translation and linguistic theories of literary criticism. They continue, literary theory of translation is an activity that is important for comparing literary studies, it is considered as highly subjective. Absolutely not, linguistic theory of translation is distinguished to have more objective source for studies of translation since they use different linguistic theories. Consequently, the theory of translation is considered to be part of a general linguistic theory.

3. Problems in Translation

When trying to translate, translators may face some obstacles and problems. These problems are difficulties which result in stopping the process of translation. According to Ghazala, "*translation problems can be due to sound, lexis (word), grammar, and style*" (1995: 18). Ghazala (1995) divided them into: grammatical, lexical, phonological, and stylistic. In this study, the researcher deals only with grammatical problems.

3.1 Lexical Problems

Lexical problems are the most that are committed by students because they think that translation is only at word level. There are many kinds of such problems, e.g., polysemous words, synonyms, idioms, proverbs, metaphors, collocations, technical terms, proper nouns, political establishments, titles, and geographical terms.

3.2 Phonological Problems

This type of problems focuses on sounds (ibid.). Phonologically, it is the translation of sounds from SL into TL because of specific purposes. It is related literature, especially poetry, and advertising texts. Wightwitch & Gaafar (2005) says that the translation is very complex, and many problems occurred when trying to make the translated poem like the original one in terms of phonological structure.

3.3 Stylistic Problems

Style is related to the meaning, if the style is ignored, a part of meaning will be ignored. Scholars have paid a great attention to stylistic problems because of its importance. Ghazala (1995:18) says "*when the translator tries to translate, he finds a kind of non-equivalence in some points such as formality vs. informality, simple vs. complex style, short vs. long sentences, passive vs. active style, and ambiguity. This non-equivalence leads to many problems*".

3.4 Grammatical Problems

Baker (2001) says that Arabic as a Semitic language and English as a Germanic language belongs to different families. So, Arabic and English grammars are different. She adds, each language has its particular grammatical rules, elements, categories, and features.

According to her, Baker quoted, *“Grammar is the set of rules which determine the way in which units such as words and phrases can be combined in a language and the kind of information which has to be made regularly explicit in utterances”* (2001:83). Therefore, students committed many problems when they translate from SL into TL.

Ghazala (2008) writes about the problems in translation of English-Arabic texts and their solutions. He says that translation is a way of rendering the meaning of the source text into the target text. Ghazala (2002) mentions the components of a language needed in the process of translation, they are grammar, vocabulary, style and phonology. He signifies, problems of translation are those difficulties that face the translator when dealing with two languages. In the same vein, those difficulties are as a result of a complicated source language grammar, different target language grammar and different target language word order. In conclusion, grammatical problems in English-Arabic translation are the most common problems because of their different grammatical systems. Lawley (2004) writes that the learning a foreign language might be created many mistakes, and English teachers should pay their attention to students' grammatical mistakes committed by them in their writing. They should be aware of grammatical mistakes.

Many studies have been done dealing with translation problems. Jaback (2007) has written a study to identify the problems that 200 Arab students face in translating Arabic into English. The findings reported that 55% were linguistic problems; 69% grammatical problems, 50% lexical problems, and 46% were morphological problems. Al-Nakhalah (2007) investigates the difficulties that face Palestinian students of English at Al-Quds Open University in the Gaza Strip while translating tenses from English to Arabic. He uses a random sample composed of 185 students (male & female) at Al-Quds Open University in the Gaza Strip in the first term of the academic year 2006/2007. The researcher finds that the most difficulties in translation committed are in tenses.

AlShehab (2009) investigates the difficulties encountered while translating military expressions from English into Arabic and vice versa among military personnel who studied English as a second language in the Jordanian Academy. To achieve the objectives of the study, English and Arabic military texts were given to the sample of military personnel. The results of the study finds the most common problems are grammatical ones.

AlShehab study (2013) aims at investigating a number of syntactic difficulties that the Jordanian English students encountered in translating sentences from Arabic into English at Irbid National University in Jordan. A validated test of 20 Arabic sentences was given to a random sample of 20 students (2010-2011) to be translated into English. The difficulties were computed, analyzed, and categorized into syntactic problems (omission and addition, and grammar). The results revealed that the students committed 292 errors. The number of omission errors was 54, additions errors were 42, while the number of grammatical was 196 errors.

Al-Imian (2014) writes a study aims at identifying most syntactic and grammatical problems that students encounter when translating military texts. The study used a sample of translation students at the University of Jordan, whilst the current study used a sample of Jadara University students. The study revealed many syntactic and grammatical problems such as; addition, omissions, and word order as a syntactic problems. Al-Ma'ani (2015) investigates the most common problems committed by translation students at Sultan Qaboos University, Oman. To achieve the objectives of the study, a translation test containing several military expressions was given to the students. The results of the study found that the translation students in Al Sultan Qaboos University struggled to understand technical information, technical expressions and collocations.

Reviewing some of the previous studies, it could be seen that (Al-Nakhalah, 2007; Jaback, 2007; AlShehab, 2009, 2013; Al-Imian (2014). Al-Nakhalah (2007) investigates the difficulties that face Palestinian students of English at Al-Quds Open University (the Gaza Strip in the first term of the academic year 2006/2007) while translating tenses from English to Arabic. AlShehab (2009) investigates the difficulties encountered while translating military expressions from English into Arabic. Similarly, AlShehab study (2013) aims at investigating a number of syntactic difficulties that the Jordanian English students encountered in translating sentences from Arabic into English at Irbid National University in Jordan. Regarding the tools used, Al-Nakhalah (2007) uses a text given to a random sample composed of 185 students (male & female). The researcher finds that the most difficulties in translation committed are in tenses. While AlShehab (2009) uses two texts English and Arabic military texts that were given to the sample of military personnel. The results of the study finds the most common problems are grammatical ones. AlShehab (2013) used a validated test of 20 Arabic sentences; it was given to a random sample of 20 students to be translated into English. The results revealed that the students committed omission errors, additions errors, while the number of grammatical was the highest with 196 errors.

4. The Problem Statement

The previous studies focus on analyzing the syntactic errors committed by students, and they use literary texts to be analyzed. No studies have been done in using scientific or technical texts to be translated into English or Arabic except the study of AlShehab (2009). He tackles with technical military text. On the other side, environmental translation is nearly ignored although it is considered one of technical translation. AlShehab (2018), in his last paper, he tried to fill the gap resulted from ignoring such subject, and he wrote a study dealing with examining the ability of translation students in translating environmental expressions and sentences at Jadara University in Jordan. Other than, no studies have been recently done in studying problems that encounter students when translating English or Arabic environmental texts. This study comes to fill the need of such research in utilizing environmental text. On other words, it could

be said that it is the first in the realm of translation studies. It studied the grammatical problems (errors or mistakes) committed by Jadara University translation students when translating Arabic environmental text into English.

4.2 Objectives of the Study

The study aims at investigating the grammatical errors committed by translation students when translating Arabic environmental text into English.

4.3 Questions of the Study

To achieve the previous objective, the following question is set up:

What are the general grammatical problems committed by translation students when translating Arabic environmental text Arabic into English at Jadara University in Jordan?"

4.4 Significance of the Study

Environment as a part of the world we live, it should be studied and known, thus, studying the environment and its problems may be understood by an active tool. This is embedded in translation, as it is one of the important tools that could give us a significant knowledge about what has been happening in the world. The importance of this study is derived from its subject; it deals with translating Arabic environmental text into English, therefore, it gives us some data about the environment throughout the process of translation. The study is the first done at the Jordanian academic level, it comes to connect between the scientific knowledge and language, and it deals with the environment from the one hand, and the translation, on the other hand. Students can get many advantages from this study in understanding environmental expressions that are neglected at the realm of literary field. In addition to doing more translation researches like this kind. By following this benefit, decision makers could begin in issuing environmental translation textbooks at graduate and undergraduate levels.

4.5 Limitation of the Study

The study is limited to its sample and the environmental text. The sample used is only 20 translation students, and the text is just Arabic to be translated into English. The scope of this study is Jadara University in Jordan, so, the results cannot be generalized.

5. Methods of the Study

5.1 The Sample of the Study

The random sample of 20 translation students was selected from English Department at Jadara University in Jordan; they enrolled in the second semester of the academic year (2017-2018). The students had studied different courses in translation from English into Arabic and vice-versa, and all of them are the same in their educational background.

5.2. Data Collection

For achieving the aims of the study, the researcher selects an English text of 10 long environmental sentences to be an Arabic text from the book titled "environmental science" written by Elden D. Enger and Bardely F., Smith.

To apply committee translation, the English text exposed to two professors at Yarmouk University in Jordan, they were asked to translate it into Arabic. For applying back translation, the Arabic text was given to another two professors at Jadara University to translate it into English. The translation was compared with its original in the book, and then the final Arabic text was set up to examine students, as in Appendix A (p.15). The reliability was achieved by using test-retest method. The text was presented to five students outside the sample, then they were examined after two weeks, their results were computed and compared by the use of "Pearson Equation" between the scores of the two tests, followed by calculating correlation coefficient that was 92%. Therefore, the validity and the reliability of the Arabic environmental text were confirmed.

5.3 Data Analysis

For analyzing data, and to investigate the grammatical problems (errors) committed by translation students, the Arabic text was given to the sample to translate it into English. Quantitatively, the grammatical problems or errors were computed and tabulated in tables, followed by qualitative analysis in discussing these problems. Justifications for their problems committed were clarified from the researcher's point of view.

6. Results and Discussions

6.1 For answering the question of the study: *What are the general grammatical problems committed by translation students when translating Arabic environmental text into English at Jadara University in Jordan?"*

Previously, AlShehab (2018) has done his first paper aims at recognizing the students' ability in translating environmental sentences and expressions. In his current paper, the researcher deals only with analyzing errors or mistakes committed by translation students when translating Arabic environmental text into English without recognizing their level.

Table 2 indicates that the students committed 170 errors with 85%, it reflects the difficulty in translation. The high rate of difficulty may be ascribed to students' weakness in translation to English. Grammatical problems in this study consist of five categories; *Verb to be*, *Subject Verb Agreement*, *Wrong Word Usage*, *Sentence Fragment*, and *Pronouns*. For figuring the errors or mistakes, frequencies and percentages were computed as shown in Table 2.

Table 1: Students' Answers for Test Sentences

No. Students	No. Sentences	No. tested Items	No. Wrong Answers	No. Correct Answers	% Wrong Answers
20	10	200	170	30	85

To identify the grammatical problems encountered by students, frequencies, percentages and ranks were computed as in table (2).

Table 2: Frequencies, percentages and ranks of grammatical problems

No.	G. Problems	Frequencies	%	Rank
1	Verb to be	25	14.7	4
2	Subject Verb Agreement	40	23.5	2
3	Wrong Word Usage	45	26.5	1
4	Sentence Fragment	35	20.6	3
5	Pronouns	25	14.7	4
All		170	100	

Table 2 indicates the results of grammatical problems when translating Arabic environmental text into English. Based on the table 2, errors in the use of *Wrong Word Usage* constituted an over whelming majority. There are 45 occurrences with the highest percentage of (26.5), the second rank is for *Subject Verb Agreement* mistakes, they have got (23.5), followed by *Sentence Fragment* with a percentage of (20.6). While the mistakes of *Pronouns* and *Verb to be* have got (14.7) percentage for each of them. The discussion of these mistakes as follows:

6.1.1 Wrong Word Usage

The problem of *Wrong Word Usage* means using different unsuitable words and phrases in translation that caused many errors and incorrect meaning. The meaning of the sentence is changed and become odd to the reader. In this study, many wrong words are used as the following:

The Arabic sentence البيئية، كنظام وظيفي، له علاقات طبيعية بين مكوناته العضوية وغير العضوية is translated by some students as: *environment, as a functional system, has normal relatives between its organic and non-organic components.* البيئية، كنظام وظيفي، له أقارب عادي بين عناصرها العضوية وغير العضوية. Here they use the word *relatives* أقارب instead of *relations* علاقات. This makes the meaning incorrect.

The Arabic phrase وهذا ما يسمى بالتوازن البيئي is translated by some students as: *this said ecology balance* وقال هذا التوازن الإيكولوجي. They used the word *said* instead of *called*, which change the meaning because the correct translation used passive voice, while in students' translation active voice is utilized. The correct translation is *this is called environmental balance*. They also translated the Arabic word البيئي as *ecology*, which means علم البيئة.

The first phrase is translated by some students as *through the reasons that threat the environmental balance are* من خلال الأسباب التي تهدد التوازن البيئي هي *among* بين and *factors* العوامل to *through* خلال and *reasons* الأسباب, the meaning of the

phrase is changed. The second Arabic phrase *اختفاء الكثير من الانواع وازالة الغابات* is translated by some students as *disappear of many kinds and forestation* that means in Arabic *تختفي العديد من الأنواع والتشجير*, the translation here is not correct, they used the English verb *disappear* instead of the English noun *disappearance*, some students utilized the word *kinds* (sorts or types) instead of *species* (a set of animals or plants that have the same characteristics). They used the word *forestation* *التشجير* instead of *deforestation* *ازالة الغابات*, they are opposite words in meaning and give an opposite and incorrect translation.

The Arabic sentence *ومن بين العوامل التي تهدد التوازن البيئي: اختفاء الكثير من الانواع وازالة الغابات* The correct translation is among the factors that threaten the environmental balance is: *the disappearance of many species and deforestation*.

The Arabic sentence *ويعد الاحترار العالمي والمطر الحمضي من أخطر المشكلات البيئية الناتجة عن تلوث الغلاف الجوي* is translated by some students as *overall heating and acid rain are considered the nearly all serious environmental problems that resulting from atmospheric pollution*. They used the phrase *overall heating* *وعموما تدفئة* instead of *global warming* *الاحترار العالمي*. Others used the phrase *the nearly all serious* *أخطر تقريبا جميع الخطيرة* instead of *the most serious* *أخطر*. The more correct translation is *global warming and acid rain are considered the most serious environmental problems that resulting from atmospheric pollution*.

6.1.2 Subject Verb Agreement

The subject should match the verb in its number as singular or plural in any sentence. So, the subject and the verb must be same kind in terms of singular or plural. For example, *smart students studies hard to get a higher degree*. The correct sentence is *smart students study hard to get a higher degree*. Many errors have been occurred through the process of students' translation as follows:

The Arabic sentence *البيئة, كنظام وظيفي, له علاقات طبيعية بين مكوناته العضوية وغير العضوية* has been translated by a number of students as *the environment, as a functional system, have normal relations between its organic and non-organic components*. Here, the students used the word *have* instead of *has*. The environment is a singular word, it should has a singular verb *has*. Some students use *their* instead of *its*, it is incorrect use, it means in Arabic *مكوناتهم* but the correct is *مكوناته*, the word *their* signifies to plural type while the environment is singular.

The Arabic sentence *ومن العوامل التي تهدد التوازن البيئي اختفاء الكثير من الانواع وازالة الغابات* is translated into English as; *among the factors that threaten the environmental balance is the disappearance of many species and deforestation*. They used the word *is*, it is a singular verb to be, while the correct one is *are* because we mean a plural word *factors* not a singular word *factor*. Some students translated *as threatens* not *threaten*, they must follow the rules of such grammar.

The Arabic sentence *يقول علماء البيئة أن تلوث المياه والتربة يضر بالحيوانات والبيئة على حد سواء* is translated by some students as *environmentalists says that water and soil pollution harms the environment and animals alike*. They used some singular verbs, e.g., *says* and *harms* for plural subject *environmentalists* that means *علماء البيئة*. The correct translation is; *environmentalists say that water and soil pollution harm the environment and animals alike*.

6.1.3 Verb to be

Because *Verb to be* does not appear clearly in Arabic, students may ignore or forget to use it when the process of translation into English. Errors are commonly spread among Arab students by deleting it unintentionally. In this study *Verb to be* errors have occurrence of 25 occurrences with 14.7%.

The Arabic sentence *ونتيجة لذلك, البيئيون سعيون جداً عندما تحقق أخيراً الخلق البيئي*. It is translated by some students as; *as a result, environmentalists was very happy when environmental ethics has finally been achieved*. The use the verb to be *was* instead of *were*. Another errors regarding verb to be in the Arabic sentence *وهذا ما نعتبره من الأخلاقيات البيئية*, it is translated as *this are what we consider to be of environmental ethics*. They use *are* instead of *is*.

In the same vein of analysis, students translate the Arabic sentence *ويعد الحر العالمي والمطر الحمضي من أخطر المشكلات البيئية الناتجة عن تلوث الغلاف الجوي* as *global warming and acid rain was considered the most serious environmental problems that caused atmospheric pollution*. They used the incorrect verb to be *was* instead of *are*.

6.1.4 Sentence Fragment

It is a partial sentence; it lacks a subject or a verb, and may be it lacks both of them. They constituted 35 occurrences with 20.6%. For example, the Arabic sentence *البيئة, كنظام طبيعي له علاقات طبيعية بين مكوناته العضوية وغير العضوية* has been translated by some students as *a functional system, has normal relations between its organic and non-organic components*. They delete the subject which is the *environment*. Some students translate it as; *Has a normal relation a functional system between its organic or non-organic components*. The English sentence is incorrect; the order of the sentence is mixed. The meaning in Arabic is *له علاقة طبيعية نظام وظيفي بين مكوناته العضوية أو غير العضوية*. It is far away from the exact meaning, it is neither has a subject, nor has a complete verb. The correct translation is *the environment, as a functional system, has normal relations between its organic and non-organic components*

The Arabic sentence *ومن العوامل التي تهدد التوازن البيئي اختفاء الكثير من الأنواع وإزالة الغابات* has been translated by some students as *among the factors of environmental balance are the disappearance of many species and deforestation*. They ignore the verb *threaten*, so, the Arabic meaning is *من بين عوامل التوازن البيئي هي اختفاء العديد من الأنواع وإزالة الغابات*, the ignorance of the verb *threaten* makes the sentence incorrect because the English phrase *the disappearance of many species and deforestation* becomes from the factors of environmental balance which is an opposite meaning. The most correct translation is *among the factors that threaten the environmental balance are the disappearance of many species and deforestation*.

The Arabic sentence *ودعا البيئيون الى التخلص من النفايات الخطرة وحماية الأنواع المهددة بالانقراض* has been translated by a number of students as *environmentalists hazardous waste disposal and the protection of endangered species* *دعاة حماية البيئة التخلص من النفايات الخطرة وحماية الأنواع المهددة بالانقراض*, here the students delete the verb *asked for*. As a result, the meaning of the sentence is entirely changed. The correct translation is *environmentalists asked for hazardous waste disposal and the protection of endangered species*.

The Arabic sentence *حيث يقوم هذا النظام بتحويل طاقة الشمس والرياح الى طاقة كهربائية مفيدة للمصانع والشركات والبيوت* is translated by some students as *where this system could the sun's energy and wind into electrical energy useful for factories*, *حيث يمكن هذا النظام أن الشمس والرياح إلى طاقة كهربائية مفيدة، بطاقة للمصانع*. By deleting the verb *converts*, the translation of the sentence is incorrect. The correct translation is *where this system could convert the sun's energy and wind into electrical energy useful for factories*.

6.1.5. Using the Wrong Pronoun

In English, the personal pronouns are: *I, you, he, she, it, we, and they*. These pronouns are used as subjects, while *me, you, him, her, their, and our* are used as objects. *You* and *it* as personal pronouns have only one form for the subject and the object. Relative pronouns are: *who, whom, where, when, which, whose*. These pronouns form the most common errors in translation and writing. In this study, pronoun errors have got the occurrence of 25 with 14.7%, it has achieved the last rank of errors. It signifies to students' reasonable skills in translating pronouns. For example, the Arabic sentence *يقول علماء البيئة: أن تلوث المياه والتربة يضر بالحيوانات والبيئة على حد سواء* has been translated by a number of students as *you say that water and soil pollution harm the environment and animals alike*. They used the personal pronoun *you say* *أنتم* as a subject instead of *they say* *هم*, by this, they deleted the subject *environmentalists*, normally, it is incorrect. Another example, *لذلك طالبوا باستخدام نظام الطاقة المتجددة* has been translated by some students as *they called for them the use of renewable energy system*, they added the object pronoun *them*, which makes the meaning odd. The use of the pronoun in this case is a big mistake and the best translation is; *they called for the use of renewable energy system*, without the need to use the pronoun.

The Arabic sentence *حيث يقوم هذا النظام بتحويل طاقة الشمس والرياح الى طاقة كهربائية* is translated by some students as; *when this system converts the sun's energy and wind into electrical energy*. They used the relative pronoun *when* instead of *where*. Another example, *وهذا ما يسمى بالتوازن البيئي* is translated by some students as *where is called environmental balance*. They used the word *where* instead of *which*, it is incorrect. The most correct translation is *where this system converts the sun and wind energy into electrical energy*.

It could be seen that most of students have done mistakes when translating between both English-Arabic languages. They committed a variety of errors or mistakes. It is ascribed to their weakness in translation skills regarding the structure of the two languages. The highest percent of errors is for *Wrong Word Usage*. It is attributed to their bad knowledge of English equivalencies for Arabic words. The second rank is for *Subject Verb Agreement* mistakes, and students leaned to make many *Subject Verb Agreement* errors in their translations. This may be ascribed to different structure between both languages. In students' translation, they didn't follow the English structure; they deal with the singular as plural without adding (*s* or *es*) for singular subject. The third rank is for *Sentence Fragment* errors by ignoring the subject, and by this, the meaning of the sentence is changed. As a final point, the mistakes of *Pronouns* and *Verb to be* had got the last rank.

The study meets most of the previous studies in analyzing errors or problems committed by students when translating Arabic or English text into its target. In opposite, no studies could meet this study in its analysis, the study dealt with specific issues pertaining to translation of Arabic environmental text into English.

7. Recommendations and Suggestions

The results found could cover the way for developing valuable recommendations. They also could reflect positive implications to improve environmental translation for those interested in such subject. In the light of the previous results, the following recommendations and suggestions are set up:

1. Issuing environmental course to be studied as translation textbook for all translation students at all Jordanian Universities.
2. Conducting outdoor activities in translation, especially environmental translation.
3. Interdisciplinary translation approach should be prepared to be studied for students at various school levels.
4. Doing more practical and empirical researches in environmental translation.
5. Doing more survey researches dealing with how to improve environmental translation.
6. Encouraging researchers to write more researches by offering financial rewards for excelling in their researches.

8. Conclusion

The previous results were anticipated, and the students need the necessary translation skills to translate between both Arabic-English. In the same vein, the students are not professional in their translation, particularly, from Arabic to English. Therefore, and in spite of the fact that students committed a lot of mistakes, some students were skilled in their translation without any mistakes. More to the point, this study addressed some problems that have never been mentioned in the previous studies. It focused on five grammatical problems (*Verb to be*, *Subject Verb Agreement*, *Wrong Word Usage*, *Sentence Fragment*, and *Pronouns*) that are nearly not tackled previously. It deals, for the first time, with translation of Arabic environmental text into English. In the same research line, the previous discussion reflects the need for more environmental courses to be taught for translation students to become more professional in their translation, especially in environmental translation. In this respect, recommendations and suggestions were set up to decrease translation problems committed, and to improve environmental translation.

References

- Al-Ma'ani, M. (2015). "The Contextual over the Referential in Military Translation". *English Language Teaching*, 8, 1-16.
- Al-Imian, T. (2014). "Problems and Strategies of Translating English Military Texts into Arabic". Unpublished M.A. Thesis, The University of Jordan, Amman.
- Al-Shehab, M. (2009). "Issues In Translating Military Expressions and Texts between English and Arabic". Unpublished PhD Thesis, University of Science and Technology, Malaysia.
- Al Shehab, M. (2013). Investigating the Syntactic Difficulties which Encounter Translation Students at Irbid National University in Jordan from Arabic into English. *AWEJ, Special issue on Translation*, (2), (129-148).
- Al-Shehab, M. (2014). "The Translatability of Military Expressions by M.A.SS in Translation at Yarmouk University in Jordan". *International Journal of Comparative Literature & Translation Studies*, 2, 6-13.
- Al-Shehab, M. (2018). The ability of students' translation in translating Arabic environmental expressions into English at Jadara University in Jordan. *International Journal of English Linguistics*, 8, No. 6.
- Aziz, Y. Lataiwish, M. (2000). *Principles of translation*. Benghazi. Dar Anhda Alarabia.
- Baker, M. (2001). *In other words: A course book on translation*. London: Routledge
- Brislin, W. (1976). *Translation: Application and Research*. New York: Gardner Press Inc.
- Catford, J. C. (1965). *A Linguistic Theory of Translation: An essay in applied linguistics*. London: Oxford University.
- Farghal, M. (1994). The Pragmatics of Insallah in Arabic Jordanian. *Multilingual*, 14(3): pp. 253-270.
- Farghal, M., Shunnaq, A. (1999). *Translation With Reference to English and Arabic*. A practical guide. Irbid: Dar al-hilal for translation.
- Ghazala, H. (1995). *Translation as Problems and Solutions*. A Course book for University Students and Trainee Translators, Syria: Malta: ELGA Publication.
- Ghazala, H. (2002). *Translation as Problems and Solutions*. A Course book for University Students and Trainee Translators, Syria: Dar El Kalam El Arabi.
- Ghazala, H. (2008). *Translation as problems and solutions*. Dar El-Ilm Lilmalayin.
- Ivir, V. (1981). Formal correspondence vs. translation equivalence revisited, *Poetics Today* 2, 4:51-9.
- Jabak, O. (2007). *Analysis of the Most Commonly Recurring Difficulties Facing Arab Students When Translating into English*. (Unpublished master's dissertation). University of Salford.UK.
- Lawley, J. (2004). A preliminary report on a new grammar checker to help students of English as a foreign language. *Arts and Humanities in Higher Education: An International Journal of Theory, Research and Practice*, 3 (3), 331-342.

- McGuire, B. S. (1980). *Translation Studies*. Methuen and Co London and New York.
- Newmark, P. (1991). *About Translation*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters Ltd.
- Nida, E. and Taber, C. (1969). *The Theory and Practice of Translation*. Netherlands: E.J. Brill.
- Shunnaq, A. (1993). Lexical Incongruence in Arabic-English Translation due to Emotiveness in Arabic, *In Turjumān (2.2)*, pp. 37-63.
- Tengku, Sepora, T. M., Moindjie, M.A. (2006). *Text-Wise in Translation*. Selangor Press.
- Wightwitch, J. & Gaafar, M. (2005). *Easy Arabic Grammar*. McGraw: Hill Professional.

Appendix A

Arabic Text

Dear translation student

Regards

Between your hands an Arabic text, please translate into English. Your translations will be processed under perfect privacy. In a case that you want to look through the results of this study. You can contact the researcher at the following e-mail:

E-mail: jordan_1948@yahoo.com.

Your consideration is highly appreciated.

□

البيئة, كنظام وظيفي, له علاقات طبيعية بين مكوناته العضوية وغير العضوية, وهذا ما يسمى بالتوازن البيئي. ومن بين العوامل التي تهدد التوازن البيئي اختفاء الكثير من الأنواع ويعد الاحتباس العالمي والمطر الحمضي من أخطر المشكلات البيئية الناتجة عن وإزالة الغابات تلوث الغلاف الجوي, وتؤثر بشدة على التوازن البيئي. ودعا البيئيون (دعاة حماية البيئة) الى التخلص من النفايات الخطرة وحماية الأنواع المهددة بالانقراض. يقولون أن تلوث المياه والتربة يضر بالحيوانات والبيئة على حد سواء, لذلك دعوا الى استخدام نظام الطاقة المتجددة, حيث يحول هذا النظام طاقة الشمس والرياح الى طاقة كهربائية مفيدة للمصانع والشركات والبيوت, وهذا يعتبر من الأخلاقيات البيئية. ولذلك, أنصار البيئة سعداء جداً لأن الأخلاقيات البيئية قد تحققت أخيراً.

Appendix B

English Translation of Arabic Text

The environment, as a functional system, has normal relations between its organic and non-organic components, this is called environmental balance. Among the factors that threaten the environmental balance are the disappearance of many species and deforestation. Global warming and acid rain are considered the most serious environmental problems that resulting from atmospheric pollution, and affect strongly on environmental balance. Environmentalists asked for hazardous waste disposal and the protection of endangered species. They say that water and soil pollution harm the environment and animals alike. So, they called for the use of renewable energy system, where this system converts the sun and wind energy into electrical energy useful for factories, businesses, and homes, and this is considered from environmental ethics. Therefore, the environmentalists are very happy because environmental ethics has been finally achieved.

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